

Technical Paper

Automated pallet loading of irregularly shaped objects: A deep reinforcement learning and multi-criteria optimization method

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ABSTRACT

Palletizing in manufacturing presents a formidable challenge, particularly when dealing with irregularly shaped objects. This paper introduces a novel approach to optimizing pallet loading scenarios integrating Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) and heuristic methods with stability assessment and constraint satisfaction within an automated palletization pipeline. The proposed solution consists of four key components. First, each object undergoes preprocessing, involving shape extraction from data files and the generation of metrics to evaluate stability and palletization suitability. Subsequently, object selection is performed using either a DRL agent—trained to predict optimal loading sequences—or a rule-based prioritization strategy, enabling a comparative analysis of selection methods. Constraint satisfaction techniques are then applied to narrow down the search space for candidate placement positions. Finally, optimal object placement is determined using a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach that evaluates candidate positions and orientations based on weighted performance criteria. The proposed framework is validated through a case study in the architectural aluminum industry, demonstrating its pivotal role in automating a production line responsible for sorting and packaging customer orders.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, international trade has expanded dramatically, integrating businesses of all sizes into a global supply chain. Linking manufacturers, suppliers, retailers, and consumers from different parts of the globe has placed significant demands on supply chain practices [1]. In Europe alone, e-commerce generates an estimated business-to-customer turnover of nearly 1 billion euros, with an expected annual growth rate of 8 % [2]. In response to the increasing demand, the manufacturing and logistics industries are making great efforts to transition from manual labor to automation, driven by recent advancements in robotics and AI to reduce costs and enhance competitiveness in today's market [3]. Given the high volume of trade, efficient and cost-effective packaging is essential. One of the key strategies for maintaining product costs lower and reducing environmental footprint is optimizing the packaging space while simultaneously ensuring cargo safety.

Given the inherent complexity of these types of optimization problems and their significance in the field of logistics, researchers have devoted substantial efforts to categorizing them and devising solutions

for several decades [4]. In the research community, these challenges are broadly classified under Cutting and Packing Problems, which encompass a wide range of logistical scenarios such as container loading, pallet stacking, and placement optimization [5]. Terminologies such as the Pallet Loading Problem (PLP), Nesting, Bin Packing Problem (BPP), and Knapsack Problem among others are closely associated [6]. The common objective is to efficiently arrange a collection of smaller items (cargo), within a set of larger items (e.g. pallets, containers, etc.) in a way that optimizes an objective function while satisfying specific constraints. Variations of these problems are primarily distinguished and classified based on the specific objective function they aim to optimize, along with the distinctive characteristics and constraints associated with each case [7].

The non-polynomial nature of these problems has driven researchers to employ different approaches and has been the topic of discussion for multiple research papers over the years [8,9]. The work presented in this manuscript could be classified as a Pallet Loading Problem (PLP); however, it introduces a novel approach to incorporate irregularly shaped objects, in comparison with traditional methods that typically consider only rectangular items such as boxes [10]. The issue of

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efficiently arranging multiple items on a pallet is encountered across various industrial sectors, ports, and other logistical areas. Given the problem's significance and the unprecedented volume of today's global trade, automating the palletization process is increasingly gaining attention. Although robotic palletizers are already deployed in industrial applications, their automation capabilities are often limited when handling highly heterogeneous and irregularly shaped cargo [11]. While existing systems can handle picking and placing of standardized objects, they frequently rely on manual labor and operator expertise for object selection, intricate handling, orientation and placement adjustments, as well as stability assurance in complex palletizing scenarios.

Manufacturing companies have long sought automation to enhance competitiveness, balancing productivity, cost, quality, and flexibility [12]. The adoption of smart and reconfigurable manufacturing systems has enabled factories to adapt to changing production requirements, offering increased flexibility and efficiency in handling diverse and intricate products [13]. Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence and the rise of Deep Learning have opened new possibilities for addressing complex industrial challenges [14,15]. Integrating AI-driven decision-making with cyber-physical systems [16] further enhances the adaptability and accuracy of product perception and modeling [17]. These developments in AI-enhanced robotics and smart manufacturing create a strong foundation for advancing automated palletization systems that combine Deep Reinforcement Learning with established optimization algorithms.

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a decision-making framework in which an agent learns to take optimal actions by interacting with an environment. Traditional RL methods, such as Q-learning and policy gradient approaches, typically rely on lookup tables to store values or policies for different states [18]. While effective for simpler tasks, these methods often face challenges in large-scale problems due to memory limitations and computational constraints [19]. Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) addresses these limitations by replacing tabular representations with deep neural networks [20]. By utilizing deep neural networks for value function approximation and policy learning, DRL aligns with the broader definition of deep learning as outlined in [21].

This work aims on presenting a novel approach to solving the Pallet Loading Problem (PLP) for irregularly shaped objects. More specifically, a configurable software package, leveraging Deep Reinforcement Learning, optimization algorithms, and heuristics, is developed for determining optimized stacking configurations. As discussed in the following sections, this work goes beyond the traditional nesting algorithms by incorporating physics-based evaluations that satisfy stability constraints and account for object equilibrium positions, towards the prevention of item damage and the maximization of space utilization. This AI-based tool, which supports dynamic object selection, can be used as an enabling technology for robotized packaging cells for applications in industry and logistics which are currently performed manually due to their dependence on human improvisation and experience.

This manuscript is organized into eight sections, including this introductory section. The purpose of Section 2 is to discuss the findings of previous relevant activities. Section 3 presents the industrial problem and the case study in the architectural aluminum industry, where the proposed approach contributes to its production line automation. Section 4 analyzes the overall framework's architecture and the principles underlying each component, while Section 5 details their implementation. The experimental results are presented and discussed in Section 6. Finally, the manuscript presents the conclusions of this work and highlights the authors' future activities.

2. Relevant work

Cutting and Packing Problems (C&P) are commonly classified under Combinatorial Optimization Problems (COPs). COPs are a class of mathematical and computational problems that involve making discrete choices from a finite set of possibilities while satisfying a set of

constraints [22]. A key characteristic of these problems is that the number of possible solutions grows exponentially with the size of the problem, rendering them non-polynomial complexity problems. Despite the computational complexity required to find guaranteed optimal solutions for such issues, researchers have shown substantial interest in devising and evaluating exact approaches [23,24].

While the search space for the Pallet Loading Problem is finite, in most application scenarios it is still too large for an exhaustive search to be a realistic option. For this reason, most research papers in the literature deploy heuristic methods to find solutions of acceptable quality quickly. Thorough comparisons between heuristic methods have been conducted over the years [25,26], featuring optimization techniques such as simulated annealing, genetic algorithms, and tabu search, among others. Additionally, heuristically decomposing a three-dimensional problem into a subset of two-dimensional problems can be utilized to reduce computational complexity and provide solutions where each subproblem is locally optimized [27]. A similar idea was followed in [28] using a two-phase algorithm in a Layer-by-Layer technique to maximize pallet volume utilization with identical boxes. The results from this study were subsequently used in [29] where the produced datasets were used to train Machine Learning algorithms to predict the most suitable pallet type when provided with the number of boxes and their dimensions.

The overwhelming majority of research papers on pallet loading and similar problems, such as container loading, focus exclusively on regular shapes like boxes. In the literature, mixed palletizing is typically defined as the arrangement of heterogeneous rectangular boxes on pallets while adhering to specific constraints [30]. The branch of Cutting and Packing Problems that has most extensively explored irregular shapes is the Nesting Problem. The objective of 2D nesting is to locate parts on a sheet material to minimize the occupied space or maximize material utilization [31]. Heuristic algorithms are predominantly employed to solve these 2D packing problems [32]. With the growing demand and maturity of applications utilizing layered and additive manufacturing, 3D nesting of irregular shapes has become an integral part of their workflow. Over the years, multiple research papers have studied this sector, offering valuable solutions for optimizing volume utilization [33] and layout optimization for 3D-printed objects [34]. However, due to the distinct nature of these problems compared to the Pallet Loading Problem, these solutions operate under different constraints and do not consider stability factors relevant to dense packaging and cargo transportation.

With recent breakthroughs in Artificial Intelligence, there has been a surge in Deep Reinforcement Learning applications aimed at solving sequential decision-making problems. Recent studies have demonstrated the effective combination of DRL with multi-objective optimization across various engineering domains, such as collaborative edge-cloud resource scheduling [35] and UAV-based trajectory planning with wireless charging [36]. Packing problems—being a subclass of sequential decision-making tasks—have been receiving increased attention as researchers explore ways to integrate DRL into optimization methods and evaluate their performance [37]. In [38], an implementation featuring an Actor-Critic DRL agent, combined with constraint programming, is used to determine the sequence, orientation, and placement of variable-sized boxes to optimize volume utilization in a packing bin. Similarly, [39] introduces an approach for online packing of boxes—without prior knowledge of their arrival order—by employing a DRL agent as part of a robotic palletizing system. Progress toward integrating non-rectangular shapes into these optimization processes is seen in [40], where a Deep Q-Network (DQN) algorithm, paired with heuristic methods, is used to solve the bin packing problem, including the selection of different box types.

The industrial applications of solutions developed for the Pallet Loading Problem hold immense potential, and researchers have been actively working to apply them to real-world industrial scenarios. For instance, [41] proposed a mathematical solution tailored for rectangular

packages, designed with simplicity and ease of use in mind. In another study, [42] introduced an automated robotic packaging system capable of calculating collision-free trajectories for the online packaging of heterogeneous carton boxes. Given the close relationship between pallet loading optimization and task planning in industrial settings, [37,43] utilizes Reinforcement Learning to enhance task planning specifically for robotic palletizers.

Following this state-of-the-art analysis, it is evident that a significant gap remains in the optimization of irregularly shaped objects for the Pallet Loading Problem (PLP) in industrial applications. This manuscript aims to address this gap by leveraging novel technologies, such as Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithms, to solve the PLP for irregular shapes while accounting for stability and loading constraints. By combining learning-based and rule-based techniques, this approach achieves a complementary integration of adaptive learning and deterministic optimization. It ensures adaptability in dynamic environments while simultaneously satisfying constraints and performing optimizations with computational efficiency.

The importance of such attributes is highlighted in applications where the objects of interest have irregular geometries involving non-symmetrical or non-structured features (e.g., structural extrusion-made beams, foiled packed items, etc.) Therefore, the resulting pallet loading optimization module can offer an effective solution for Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems, incorporating dynamic, real-time decision-making.

3. Industrial problem and motivation

The industrial problem that motivates this work originates from the architectural aluminum industry, specifically the architectural extrusion profile sector. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the scenario deals with the palletizing of profiles into personalized, customer-oriented pallets. Each customer order is unique, as it may involve a different number of profiles originating from various product identification numbers and families. Nevertheless, each pallet must be stacked effectively to ensure defect-free transfer to the customer’s site. This requires near-optimal utilization of space to achieve: a) low pallet centre of gravity, b) high pallet density with minimal spaces between the profile instances, and c) high pallet stability by "mating" the items’ geometries into equilibrium poses.

In current practice, this packaging process takes place at a completely manual workstation involving five operators per shift. These workers are assigned to machine tending operations for foiling machines that apply protective film to the profiles’ surfaces. After applying the protective foil, two operators collaborate to palletize the customer orders. This workstation places a substantial physical and cognitive burden on operators due to the intricate nature of the process. Each profile’s net weight ranges from 0.5 kg to 30 kg, and the repetitive nature of the task results in handling more than five tonnes of profiles per shift. This effectively excludes operators with less physical strength or

stamina, including female workers, middle-aged workers, or individuals with physical restrictions, due to the high risk of musculoskeletal disorders.

A notable challenge is that the profiles arrive at the workstation from the paint shop in colour-oriented batches. Operators must identify and retrieve profiles from multiple colour-oriented stacks and shuffle them into customer-specific pallets. Since the profiles lack identification numbers, barcodes, or similar markers, operators rely on visual identification by cross-referencing to paper-printed lists. This process is further complicated by the high number of profile variants, which exceed 15,000 (when colour variations are accounted for). As for the final packaging, operators consider the profiles’ geometric characteristics and are responsible for forming dense, stable, and low-centre-of-gravity pallets based on their expertise. This workflow is highly error-prone due to physical fatigue and the demands for continuous concentration, improvisation, and situational awareness. Additionally, the quality of palletizing heavily depends on the operators’ expertise, which is often undermined by labour shortages and the limited periods in which workers can sustain such ergonomically intensive roles. Automating this workstation presents an opportunity to improve working conditions and enhance human-centric production processes. The robotization of machine tending and packaging operations allows human workers to focus on higher value-added and less physically demanding tasks, significantly benefiting industrial production environments.

The implementation of a robotic system capable of automating this process requires a modular architecture equipped with dexterity, perception, and reasoning-enabling technologies. As described in [44], the robotic system consists of a manipulator that performs machine tending operations between the input and output pallets, an intermediate buffer, besides the foiling machines. Referring to the envisioned system’s architecture, depicted in Fig. 2, the management of profiles is achieved through a closed-loop process. During this process, pre-processed information about the profiles (e.g., geometries, mass, center of gravity, etc.) and real-time workstation data (e.g., item positioning, resource states, etc.) are accessible to all modules through the system’s database and digital twin.

The workflow of the envisioned solution begins once a customer order is received. The "Pallet Loading Optimizer" (PLO) module then generates a "near-optimal" stacking solution for the customer-oriented pallet. This geometric-based solution is communicated to a process planner, which schedules an optimized sequence of handling actions for the robot (e.g., pick, place, transfer, etc.) based on user-defined criteria (e.g., time, power consumption, etc.). If the schedule is not feasible (e.g., due to buffer overflow), it is either excluded or partially adjusted by modifying weights and criteria within the next planning iteration. Once the most suitable solution is selected, the generated schedule is loaded onto a service-oriented orchestrator (similar to [45]) responsible for dispatching and monitoring the execution of handling tasks.

Fig. 1. Industrial scenario: current practice and envisioned solution.

Fig. 2. Positioning of the palletizing module in the envisioned system’s overall architecture.

Neglecting the requirements for system dexterity, process planning, and perception, which are beyond the scope of this publication, a significant challenge lies in reproducing human improvisation for efficient palletizing through a non-supervised software system. The irregular shapes of the objects in this industrial scenario demand more advanced decision-making mechanisms. In comparison to standard nesting algorithms, efficient space utilization alone is insufficient. Achieving dense packaging requires accounting for object equilibrium positions and loading constraints to prevent item damage while ensuring a low center of gravity for the pallet. Furthermore, unlike existing palletizing software, the proposed solution must manage complex geometries and incorporate physics-based evaluations to satisfy stability constraints.

This publication focuses on developing a software module that extracts optimized stacking configurations to enhance robotic palletizing cells. Beyond improving the system’s reasoning attributes, the same infrastructure is also utilized to deploy a rendering pipeline for synthetic datasets. These datasets enable the accurate identification and localization of profiles during runtime using stereo vision.

The following section elaborates on the proposed methodology for addressing complex palletizing logistics problems, while Section 5 discusses its implementation for the deployment of the “PLO” module.

4. Approach

This section details the methodology behind the proposed solution for the Pallet Loading Problem. To enhance clarity, it begins with the problem’s mathematical formulation and an overview of the framework’s process, followed by a comprehensive explanation of each distinct building block.

4.1. Problem mathematical formulation

The Pallet Loading Problem can be regarded as finding an arrangement of N objects on a pallet such that the resulting layout is (i) feasible and (ii) optimized. Let $I = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ be the set of objects to be loaded, and suppose each object $i \in I$ can be placed in one of several orientations $o \in O_i$ at various positions on the pallet, indexed by p . Given these, a set of binary decision variables can be defined:

$$x_{i,o,p} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if object } i \text{ is placed with orientation } o \text{ at position } p, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

To create a feasible layout, a set of rules—referred to as constraints—must be satisfied to ensure that the placement adheres to physical and operational requirements. Mathematically, feasibility can be expressed as a function $C(X) = true$, where X represents the full set of decision variables.

The optimization goal of the layout can be represented by an objective function $f(X)$, which is either maximized or minimized based on the chosen evaluation metrics. Based on this, the PLP can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_X f(X) \\ & \text{subject to } C(X) = true, x_{i,o,p} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall i, o, p \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since each object can be placed in multiple orientations and numerous positions, the size of the search space grows exponentially with N . This combinatorial explosion, combined with the added complexity of real-world constraints, makes the problem NP-hard, rendering exact solutions impractical for large-scale industrial applications.

To address this challenge, the problem in this work is decomposed into sequential steps. The pallet is first discretized using a resolution δ to define placement positions. Then, the next object to be placed is selected, followed by constraint filtering to eliminate invalid placements. Finally, the optimal position and orientation for the selected object are determined. The key principle is that each step of the palletization process is designed as an individual optimization, ensuring that the cumulative results lead to a near-optimal overall layout.

4.2. Pallet loading optimization process overview

As previously mentioned, the solution presented in this manuscript intends to automate the palletization process of irregularly shaped objects. Fig. 3 provides a graphical overview of the solution’s process. The first step in this automated workflow is the automatic preprocessing of items and the extraction of necessary data for optimization algorithms and constraint satisfaction. To meet this requirement, an automated and configurable data processing procedure is employed. More specifically, the CAD of each object is used to extract key information, including the shape, weight, center of gravity, and custom metrics related to stability and palletization suitability.

Given that this process is only required once for each distinct object type, this step can be performed offline, by storing the extracted information in a database, saving time and computational resources. Once the data extraction and processing are completed, an optimization environment is initialized for the placement optimization loop. This initialization requires the list of objects (e.g., a customer’s order) and the used pallet’s dimensions.

The pallet loading optimization is executed by sequentially placing the objects onto the pallet until either all objects are placed, or the pallet’s capacity is reached, constrained by stability and weight distribution constraints. The first stage of the optimization loop involves

Fig. 3. Pallet loading optimization process overview.

selecting the object to place, which is performed either by a rule-based prioritization system or a Deep Reinforcement Learning agent. In the scenario where a DRL selector is used, the agent evaluates the current configuration and predicts the object that will maximize the cumulative reward in the palletization process.

Next, constraints are applied to reduce the search space by eliminating invalid positions and orientations. Each remaining candidate position and its corresponding orientation are then evaluated against optimization criteria, with the best option selected based on an overall score. For palletization problems involving 3D objects that share uniform dimensions along one axis (e.g., identical lengths), the placement search can be simplified to a 2D planar search using the objects' cross-sections. As a result, the pallet's cross-section can be represented as a grid of positions $\{(p_x, p_y)\}$, discretized at a resolution δ . This reduction in search space significantly lowers computational requirements while preserving palletization efficiency.

The process continues as the object is placed at the selected position and orientation on the pallet, generating new observations to represent the updated state of the environment. These observations are then fed to the DRL agent as input, allowing it to evaluate the current environment configuration and determine the selection for the next object. Once the placement has been completed, the optimization loop is terminated.

An additional aspect of this module includes the development of tools to enable its seamless integration into a robotized palletization scenario. These tools also support the visualization of the palletization process and aid in the development of perception and scheduling modules that can be used in a fully automated robotized palletization.

4.3. Data extraction, data processing, and metrics acquisition

The automated data extraction and processing within this optimization framework have been created to seamlessly integrate new objects in the palletization process without requiring any effort from skilled personnel. This phase is divided into two main segments.

First, the system extracts essential information about each object from a CAD file. While these files can appear chaotic in their raw format (i.e., when not read using CAD software), the approach employed in this

framework extracts each object's cross-section, material composition, and center of gravity. For products composed of multiple parts, the relevant parameters—such as individual weights and center-of-gravity points—are identified for each segment and then combined to derive the object's overall mass and center of gravity.

Once the data extraction is complete, the processing phase begins. This phase serves two key purposes, namely: a) to convert the object into a format compatible with the optimization algorithms, and b) to generate insights that improve the palletization process, either by reducing processing time or enhancing the outcome's quality.

Using the object's geometry and center of gravity, the system identifies equilibrium orientations—positions where the object can stably rest on a flat surface without requiring additional support. Based on the object's shape and stability considerations, key metrics are extracted to assess how well the object can be integrated into the pallet layout, with a focus on maintaining stability and maximizing space utilization. Finally, the objects are resized and converted into a format optimized for efficient processing by the Pallet Loading Optimization algorithms.

4.4. Object selection

For sequentially placing objects on a pallet, the placement sequence must be determined. For small collections of items, it is possible to evaluate all of them at each placement step. However, as the number of different items increases, this approach becomes computationally expensive and impractical. As a result, a prediction must be made about which item is best to place, given the current state of the pallet.

This problem can be mathematically formulated by defining a function $R(i|s)$, which represents the cumulative reward of selecting object i given the current state s . The object selection optimization for a collection of I currently available objects can be expressed by:

$$i^* = \underset{i \in I}{\operatorname{argmax}} R(i|s) \tag{3}$$

4.4.1. Static object selection: rule-based prioritization

This prediction can be static and determined in advance using predefined rules or heuristics. A straightforward approach is to sort the

available items based on a specific metric, such as volume or weight, e. g., loading heavier or larger objects first. More sophisticated heuristics may also incorporate multiple key metrics or use clustering strategies that group items by similar properties. Regardless of the chosen heuristic, these methods produce a fixed loading sequence that remains unchanged throughout the pallet loading process.

4.4.2. Dynamic object selection using deep reinforcement learning

Alternatively, a dynamic prediction considers multiple factors such as the current configuration of the pallet, the list of available objects, and other contextual parameters. In this case, object selection is not predefined but instead adapts to the evolving state of the palletization process. To achieve optimal results, the approach proposed in this manuscript employs a Deep Reinforcement Learning agent based on policy gradient methods to make dynamic predictions on the object selection. OpenAI has developed one such algorithm, called Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [46], which has showcased its potential in a wide variety of tasks ranging from robotic control [47] to playing complicated video games [48]. PPO has become very popular among the research community in recent years, due to its balance between sample efficiency, simplicity, and ease of hyperparameter tuning. The algorithm achieves this by combining ideas from existing algorithms, namely the Advantage Actor-Critic [49] and the Trust Region Policy Optimization [50]. It uses multiple agents that interact with different copies of the environment in parallel, to improve training efficiency, while restricting the amount of policy updates to improve stability. A simplified overview of the algorithm follows, but for a more detailed explanation, the interested reader is encouraged to consult the original publications.

PPO builds upon policy gradient methods, that use two deep neural networks called Policy Network (π_θ) and Value Function $V(s_t)$. The policy network takes the observed states from the environment as input and suggests actions to take as output. The value function attempts to predict the expected return G_t , also known as the discounted sum of rewards, for a given state. PPO makes use of the advantage function \hat{A}_t , which estimates the benefit of taking an action a_t in state s_t compared to the baseline estimate predicted by the value function. Inspired by TRPO, the algorithm uses the probability ratio between the new and the old policy $r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{old}}(a_t|s_t)}$ in its objective function. The probability ratio measures how much the new policy differs from the old one and clipping the updates ensures that this ratio doesn't change beyond a certain threshold.

The main objective function in PPO is the following:

$$L^{CLIP}(\theta) = \hat{E}_t[\min(r_t(\theta)\hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)\hat{A}_t)] \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is a hyperparameter called clip ratio.

The total loss function used to train an agent in PPO is the sum of this clipped PPO objective with two extra terms: the value function loss L^{VF} and an entropy bonus S :

$$L_t^{PPO}(\theta) = \hat{E}_t[L^{CLIP}(\theta) - c_1 L_t^{VF}(\theta) + c_2 S[\pi_\theta](s_t)] \quad (5)$$

The value function loss L^{VF} is used for updating the value function and improving reward predictions, while the entropy term $c_2 S[\pi_\theta](s_t)$ ensures that the agent adequately explores the action space during training.

In many scenarios where dynamic decisions must be made, the set of available actions may depend heavily on the current state. Invalid actions in Deep Reinforcement Learning and methods for addressing them have been studied extensively in recent years, with several solutions being proposed [51,52]. A common approach is to give negative rewards to the agent when selecting an invalid action. While this approach can achieve good results on small sample maps, it often struggles to scale, as the space of invalid action gets larger. To address this issue, the implementation proposed in this manuscript utilizes a technique introduced in [53]. According to this study, invalid action masking is achieved by

applying a state-dependent differentiable function during the calculation of action probability distribution. By applying a technique called gradient zeroing the algorithm ensures that invalid actions have no influence on the learning process during training [54].

To summarize, a critical component of the sequential object placement process presented in this manuscript is the dynamic selection of objects. This is achieved by utilizing a DRL agent that follows the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm. The agent processes information from the palletization environment to predict and select the optimal object for placement at each step. To enhance the efficiency of the selection process and accelerate training, invalid actions, such as selecting an object that does not exist, are omitted using invalid action masking techniques. By implementing this approach, the agent can accurately and efficiently choose the best-suited objects from predefined lists, such as customer orders, ultimately optimizing the overall palletization and packaging process.

4.5. Constraint filtering for valid placement positions

Applying constraint satisfaction techniques is a common practice when handling complex optimization problems. Constraint Programming (CP) and integer linear programming (ILP) filtering processes are commonly used in Cutting and Packing Problems [55]. There are different types of constraints and can be divided into two main categories [56], namely: a) Compulsory Constraints and b) Non-Compulsory Constraints.

Compulsory constraints are essential for any pallet loading optimization scenario with two being the most important to be considered in such problems. First, all objects should be placed within the designated pallet's volume, and second, the volumes of palletized objects should not overlap. On the other hand, non-compulsory constraints depend on the specific application scenario and the variables relevant to the implementation and optimization goals. Examples of these constraints may include considerations for weight distribution, loading priorities, stability constraints, positioning constraints, etc.

The approach proposed in this manuscript seamlessly incorporates both types of constraints to achieve accurate palletization solutions and simultaneously accelerate the optimization by reducing the search space for viable placements. An integrated filtering process is implemented before the placement optimization phase to eliminate placement configurations that do not satisfy the designated constraints. Compulsory constraints are embedded directly within the optimization loop. Meanwhile, non-compulsory constraints are partially configurable through exposed variables in configuration files, enabling user fine-tuning for optimized results tailored to specific use cases. The modular nature of the optimization process also allows for the addition of custom constraints. For instance, in robotic palletizing applications, a custom constraint could be added to ensure sufficient gripper clearance when placing and picking up objects. Fig. 4 illustrates simplified examples of configurations that violate Compulsory or Non-Compulsory constraints.

4.6. Object placement optimization

After the invalid placement configurations have been eliminated, the final step of the sequential placement approach is to select the object's optimal orientation and position on the pallet. To achieve this, a multi-criteria decision-making approach within a greedy optimization framework has been developed. Greedy algorithms [57] are commonly used in combinatorial optimization problems when considering future configurations or sequences become computationally prohibitive [58]. In the proposed approach, candidate positions are combined with each available orientation of the object to form a candidate configuration for the placement iteration. Each candidate configuration is evaluated based on a scoring function, and the configuration with the highest score is selected for final placement. Mathematically, this selection process is formulated as follows:

Fig. 4. Examples of constraint violations: a) out-of-bounds, b) overlap, c) instability, d) weight distribution.

$$(o^*, p^*) = \arg \max_{o \in O_i, p \in P} S_i(o, p) \tag{6}$$

where:

- i represents the current object,
- $o \in O_i$ denotes a feasible orientation of object i ,
- $p \in P$ denotes a candidate position of the pallet,
- $S_i(o, p)$ is the evaluation score for placing object i at position p with orientation o

A collection of m evaluation criteria, $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$, assigns a score to a candidate configuration (o, p) for object i , based on an objective function (similar to [59]). Examples include functions that assess whether the configuration introduces gaps in the packaging, or whether the placement height is above or below the pallet’s average height. Each criterion C_j can yield positive or negative values depending on whether the configuration improves or hinders the packing quality.

To make these criteria comparable, each one is individually normalized, $\widehat{C}_j(i, o, p)$, to account for variables such as pallet dimensions, object dimensions, resolution, etc. The normalized score for each criterion is multiplied by a weight, w_j , with weights representing the importance of each factor in the overall placement decision. The final score of the multi-criteria decision-making mechanism for a given configuration (o, p) for object i , visualized in Fig. 5, is expressed as:

$$S_i(o, p) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j \widehat{C}_j(i, o, p) \tag{7}$$

Weighted scoring systems are often used in multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) to balance diverse factors that contribute to the overall optimization outcome. The choice of weights offers flexibility, as they can be adapted and fine-tuned for different scenarios. The optimization approach proposed in this manuscript is designed to be easily expandable to account for variability in objects and optimization goals.

5. Implementation

This section provides detailed information on the implementation of the proposed automated pallet loading solution. The implementation examples presented here are directly related to the case study outlined in Section 3, which focuses on the metal manufacturing industry. Specifically, the palletization cargo consists of aluminum profiles in various shapes. Before packaging, these profiles are wrapped in protective foil to prevent scratches during loading, unloading, and transportation.

5.1. Data and metrics extraction from CAD files

The first step of the automated packaging process is to extract the object’s shape and material composition. This information is encoded in CAD files, specifically in “.dxf” file format. A Python script is used to read the DXF files, extract key characteristics, and generate the required images. The shape of the object is represented by polylines within the DXF file, which are used to draw the cross-section of each profile. The color of each polyline encodes the segment’s material type; whereas for this case study, black represents aluminum, while red indicates polyamide. Using the geometrical data, the algorithm is able to differentiate the segments that make up the entire profile. Given each material’s density and each cross-section’s shape (i.e., cross-section area), the system calculates the relative weight and center of gravity for each segment. The individual centers of gravity and weight data are combined to determine the assembly’s overall center of gravity and specific weight. Fig. 6 illustrates the shape extraction process and the aforementioned calculations.

As discussed in Section 3, the packaging process for aluminum profiles includes applying a protective foil. Regarding the profile’s cross-section, the object’s final shape before palletization can be approximated by its convex hull. After this step, a stability assessment is performed, along with the extraction of key metrics.

The first part of this process involves calculating the object’s equilibrium positions using its geometry and center of gravity, obtained from the previous processing step. The object can only be placed on the pallet using orientations where it rests stably on a flat surface without any external support, defining its stable orientations. Stability is assessed in 90-degree intervals, with a stability threshold applied to exclude orientations prone to tipping due to small disturbances.

Additional metrics are then extracted and stored in a database for use by the remaining modules in the optimization process. These metrics include basic properties, such as the object’s area and dimensions, as well as more complex measurements like a custom palletization fitness score, which provides insight into the object’s suitability for palletization.

Let each object i have the following metrics:

1. $M_{stable}(i)$: Stability ratio, computed as the stable side length relative to the object’s total circumference.
2. $M_{aspect}(i)$: Aspect ratio, representing the object’s height-to-width ratio.
3. $M_{ortho}(i)$: Orthogonality measure, given by the ratio of the object’s area to the area of its bounding box.
4. $M_{sym}(i)$: Symmetry measure, based on axes through the object’s center of gravity.

Fig. 5. Multi-criteria decision-making weighted scoring approach for valid configurations.

Fig. 6. Shape extraction and center of gravity point calculation for each processed object.

The palletization fitness of object i , denoted by $PF(i)$, is then calculated as a weighted sum of these sub-metrics:

$$PF(i) = w_{stable}M_{stable}(i) + w_{aspect}M_{aspect}(i) + w_{ortho}M_{ortho}(i) + w_{sym}M_{sym}(i) \tag{8}$$

With $w_{stable}, w_{aspect}, w_{ortho}, w_{sym}$ reflecting the relative importance of each factor to the final score.

Once the key characteristics of the object are extracted, the shape details are simplified to reduce unnecessary computations in the remaining steps of the palletization process. In this approach, only the convex shape of the object is retained for the final image format, with dimensions resized according to the resolution required for palletization. In the experimental setup, a resolution of 1 mm was selected to balance accuracy with computational efficiency.

The proposed automated data processing sequence is summarized in Fig. 7. It provides essential insights for the functionality of subsequent modules and results evaluation whereas its automatization enables non-supervised integration of new objects by simply interfacing to a company’s ERP database.

5.2. Static and dynamic object selection

In a sequential object placement optimization scenario, the placement order of distinct objects significantly impacts the overall optimization outcome. Packaging efficiency can vary greatly depending on the loading sequence even with the same placement optimization criteria. Due to the high computational complexity of exhaustively evaluating all possible sequences, it is necessary to predict the optimal placement order. Fig. 8 demonstrates two simplified examples of sequential object placement using the same objects, optimization criteria, and available space, with the only difference being the method used to determine the placement sequence.

5.2.1. Heuristics for loading sequence generation

Several methods and metrics for defining the loading sequence have been implemented in this work. Among others, a common approach is to sort objects based on a specific metric and feed the sorted data sequentially into the placement optimization process. A more advanced method involves clustering objects according to a selected metric,

during runtime.

To determine the optimal number of clusters, the elbow method is employed, identifying the point where adding more clusters yields diminishing returns. Once the optimal number of clusters is identified, the K-means clustering algorithm [60] partitions the objects into k clusters. The implementation ensures that within each cluster, the original priority of objects is preserved. This enables a combination of clustering and sorting to generate a final sequence that considers two different metrics.

For example, the collection can first be sorted by one metric (e.g., object volume) and then clustered using another (e.g., palletization fitness). The loading sequence is subsequently generated by prioritizing objects from the clusters with the highest palletization fitness score, while within each cluster, objects with larger volumes are loaded first. While this approach does not fully conform to the definition of hybridization as outlined in [61], it allows for a balanced consideration of multiple metrics to improve the efficiency and outcome of the palletization process, aligning with broader hybrid decision-making strategies.

5.2.2. Deep reinforcement learning object selector

For dynamic object selection, the proposed selector uses a DRL agent based on the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [46] algorithm to predict the best fit for each pallet configuration and object set. To enable this, a custom DRL simulation environment has been developed in Python to host the necessary tools and optimization algorithms. This environment follows an architecture compatible with the reliable DRL implementations in the Stable Baselines 3 collection [62,63] and is specifically configured to simulate pallet-loading scenarios similar to those in industrial applications.

For the optimization to work effectively, certain core components in the environment must be well-designed. Key functions within a DRL environment include:

1. **Action Space $\{A\}$:** This set includes all possible actions $a_t \in A$ that the agent can take at each step.
2. **Environment Observation $\{Obs(s_t)\}$:** Represents the information returned to the agent about the current state s_t of the environment.

Fig. 7. Example of CAD processing steps from the aluminum metal industry.

Fig. 8. Sequential object placement using: a) A sorted list based on the area of the parts' cross sections. b) Dynamic object selection.

3. **Reward Function $\{r_t\}$:** This function helps the agent distinguish good from bad actions for a given state s_t , influencing how it learns an optimal policy over time.

Defining and fine-tuning these functions is important for successfully modeling and solving problems with reinforcement learning and is often the most challenging aspect of the setup. An episode starts by retrieving a customer's order and initializing the environment's parameters. At each timestep t , the agent selects an action a_t , i.e., the object to place. Once constraint satisfaction and placement optimization are applied, if the object is successfully placed on the pallet, the reward r_t and the new observation $Obs(s_{t+1})$ are calculated and returned to the agent. Fig. 9 depicts a single timestep t of the DRL agent's training loop. It highlights the agent's decision-making process, including the selection of an action a_t based on its policy $\pi_\theta(a|s)$ and value $V(s)$ networks. Additionally, the figure demonstrates how the system transitions to the next state s_{t+1} while generating the observation $Obs(s_{t+1})$ and reward r_t used for the agent's update $L_t^{PPO}(\theta)$, discussed in Section 4.4.2. The episode is terminated when the selected object cannot be placed safely

on the pallet, or when all the objects in the customer's order have been successfully placed.

The action space is modeled as the selection of distinct object types available during each placement step. In our framework, each object type is assigned a unique identifier that maps directly to a discrete action, meaning that when the agent selects an action, it is effectively choosing an object type for placement. Since only one object can be selected at each timestep, the action space is naturally defined as discrete and can be implemented using the "Discrete" space from the OpenAI Gym environment framework [64]. Although this setup might seem straightforward, additional complexity is introduced through action masking (discussed in Section 4.4) to handle specific constraints in customer orders. To implement this, an additional counter parameter tracks the available quantity for each object type. When an object is placed, its corresponding counter decreases. Once the count for an object type reaches zero, the action masking mechanism modifies the probability distribution to render the respective action unavailable. This ensures the agent avoids selecting depleted object types, enabling the system to execute packaging scenarios that respect inventory constraints

Fig. 9. DRL selector training example at timestep (t).

and customer order requirements.

Accurately and concisely representing the environment’s state at each timestep is essential to help the agent learn efficient policies for selecting the optimal object. To help the agent focus on key aspects of the configuration, redundant information is omitted from the environment observation. Since objects are loaded sequentially, details below the pallet’s surface can be ignored to simplify the observation. Essential information includes the type and quantity of available objects for palletization at each step, as well as the pallet’s surface state, forming the agent’s environment observation.

Specifically, the environment’s state is composed of two main elements that integrate both local and global information. The local state is represented by discretizing the pallet surface into a grid—based on the selected resolution—where each cell stores the current height at that location. This allows the agent to detect spatial variations and gaps, enabling the identification of potentially optimal placement opportunities. In parallel, the global state is captured by a vector indicating the remaining quantities of each object type available for placement during the current loading episode. This ensures that the agent remains aware of inventory constraints and enables it to plan ahead and optimize the overall configuration with a global perspective based on object availability. These two components—the height and object availability vectors—are concatenated into a single observation vector composed of positive integer values. This unified format offers a comprehensive snapshot of the environment’s current configuration, which is dynamically updated after each placement to reflect changes in both spatial occupancy and resource availability. This state information is then passed to the DRL agent’s policy network, which outputs an action probability distribution based on the current state. After action masking is applied to filter out invalid choices, the final action is selected. Fig. 10 illustrates a simplified example of this dataflow within the Maskable PPO DRL selector.

The final critical component for the DRL is the definition of the reward function. A straightforward approach is to assign a fixed reward each time the agent successfully places an object.

This reward can be formulated as:

$$r_t = r_{base} \tag{9}$$

where r_t represents the reward at timestep t , and r_{base} is a constant reward for each successful placement.

An alternative approach involves scaling the reward proportionally to the placement evaluation score, ensuring that higher-quality placements yield greater rewards.

This can be expressed as:

$$r_t = aE(i_t) \tag{10}$$

where a is a scaling coefficient and $E(i_t)$ is the evaluation score assigned by the MCDM algorithm to the placement of object i at timestep t .

However, these approaches fail to converge toward a global optimization for the pallet’s configuration, since the agent favors objects inherently more suited for palletization over the more complex shapes.

In practice, this issue is mitigated by incorporating the palletization fitness $PF(i)$ of each object i into the reward function. With this approach, the agent receives higher rewards for successfully placing objects that are more challenging to satisfy placement criteria. One way to implement this is by adding a term inversely proportional to $PF(i)$ in the reward function, alongside the constant reward for each placement.

This can be expressed as:

$$r_t = r_{base} + \frac{\gamma}{PF(i)} \tag{11}$$

where γ is a positive coefficient that scales the additional reward.

Following this implementation, the reward is larger when $PF(i)$ is low. The key principle is to reinforce the agent for using up challenging objects, rather than repeatedly ensuring the placement of only the easiest shapes. By rewarding the placement of difficult objects, the agent explores the action space more effectively and converges toward a strategy that ultimately places all objects—yielding a more globally optimal palletization configuration.

The significance of the reward function is illustrated in Fig. 11, which depicts the average episode length, representing the number of objects successfully loaded onto the pallet per episode, for the three previously mentioned reward function implementations. The data indicate that, as expected, all implementations begin with a relatively similar number of successful placements, as the selection process is initially random. However, the palletization fitness-based reward function enables the agent to learn significantly faster compared to the fixed reward and evaluation-based reward functions. Moreover, it achieves superior results over the 1.9 million training steps. For these reasons, this reward function is selected for use in the proposed DRL selector implementation.

Multiprocessing techniques are used to generate environment instances and train the model in parallel to accelerate training. GPU acceleration is also utilized to speed up tensor computations and model updates. The model uses a feedforward multi-layer perceptron architecture within a Proximal Policy Optimization framework with integrated action masking. Hyperparameters such as the entropy coefficient and the discount factor are fine-tuned to promote exploration and increase the value of expected future rewards, respectively.

5.3. Constraint satisfaction

Constraint satisfaction is a critical component of solving the pallet loading problem. Its goal is to eliminate unfeasible and impractical pallet configurations and guide placement decisions toward an optimized outcome. The solution proposed in this manuscript implements constraints in a modular and expandable way, allowing each constraint

Fig. 10. Diagram of the pre-trained DRL selector with action masking in a simplified selection example.

Fig. 11. Average episode length for the DRL selector using 3 different reward functions, visualized using TensorBoard.

to function as an individual check that must be met for a configuration to be considered valid. This modular approach allows for seamless integration of additional constraints—such as handling and loading requirements specific to each use case—and enables fine-tuning of parameters and thresholds for existing constraints.

The first constraints the candidate configuration must satisfy are those ensuring that the object fits within the designated space and that there is no overlap between objects. While the implementation of the first constraint is straightforward, the overlap rule can be implemented with multiple methods. A common approach in pallet loading is to reserve the space occupied by each object’s bounding box. However, for irregular shapes, this method creates excessive gaps between objects, reducing optimization efficiency. In this manuscript, overlap is handled at the pixel level based on the chosen palletization resolution. The object’s bounding box and corresponding pallet area are masked and combined using a bitwise "AND" operation. If no overlap exists, the resulting grid will contain only zero values.

Once these primary checks are satisfied, non-compulsory constraints are applied to enhance pallet stability. Only stable orientations are considered when searching for an optimal configuration. For each candidate configuration, center of gravity (CoG) checks and base support evaluations are conducted. Using information obtained in the processing stage, we can verify if the area beneath the CoG meets a configurable stability threshold. If this condition is not met, the configuration may still be considered stable if a moment stability check is successful. By using the positional data of the object’s bottom surface, we approximate the torque around the CoG based on contact points with objects already placed on the pallet.

Another aspect checked during placement is the overhang. While a configuration might initially pass stability checks, excessive overhang can limit future placement options on the pallet. To address this, an overhang threshold is applied; in this implementation, a static threshold was selected, with a discounting evaluation incorporated as a criterion in the placement optimization phase. Similarly, a layering constraint improves overall pallet stability by guiding the placement of objects to gradually concentrate toward the pallet’s center, resulting in better weight distribution and enhanced dynamic stability.

Finally, height and weight constraints are enforced. The height constraint restricts the total available height for palletization, while the weight constraint considers the distribution of the cargo’s center of gravity by summing individual CoG points weighted by relative object masses to determine an overall CoG for the pallet. Limits on total weight and weight distribution improve the pallet’s structural integrity and dynamic stability during transport.

5.4. Placement optimization

Modeling and accurately evaluating what is the best placement for an object during a sequential placement process is a challenging task. As discussed in Section 4.6, the proposed solution employs multiple criteria to account for different contributing factors of a successful palletization. Fig. 12 illustrates two configurations for the sequential placement of three objects in the same sequence; intuitively, the second configuration appears more stable and efficient. To develop an algorithm that consistently produces robust configurations like this—without foreknowledge of upcoming objects—the evaluation criteria must capture the pallet’s potential at each placement step.

During development, various factors were analyzed, but experimental data indicate that five key criteria, denoted as C , have the most significant impact on the palletization process.

- C_{height} (**Placement Height**): Assesses how the candidate’s topmost point compares to the pallet’s average placement height. If the topmost point is below the average, a reward is assigned; otherwise, a penalty is imposed. Both rewards and penalties are proportional to the height difference.
- $C_{i,contact}$ (**Interlocking Contact**): Evaluates how well the candidate object interlocks with previously placed objects. This is determined by overlaying the boundary pixels on the 2D grid and counting shared edges. A larger shared boundary surface indicates a more compact and stable configuration, resulting in a positive reward.
- C_{gap} (**Unused Space**): Measures whether the placement fills existing gaps or creates new enclosed voids. If the candidate position helps seal spaces and reduce empty areas, it is positively rewarded. Conversely, placements that create large enclosed voids are penalized, as they lead to inefficient space utilization and compromise stability.
- $C_{b,contact}$ (**Bottom Surface Contact**): Determines the extent to which the object’s “stable-side” pixels make direct contact with the pallet or other profiles. A broad and uniform contact area indicates stability and is positively reinforced.
- C_{flat} (**Flat Pallet Surface**): Encourages the maintenance of a relatively flat local surface. Configurations that introduce bumps are

Fig. 12. Example of two possible configurations following the sequential placement of 3 objects.

penalized, whereas those that contribute to a flatter surface are rewarded, as they facilitate future object placements.

By applying these criteria with their user-configurable relative weights in Eq. 7 (introduced in Section 4.6), an evaluation score is assigned to each candidate configuration for every evaluated placement. These criteria are implemented at the pixel level and seamlessly integrated into the simulation environment to ensure optimal computational performance.

To evaluate the overall packing quality at runtime or offline, metrics such as total space utilization and layer density are collected. These metrics are computed after the final placement and are used primarily for post-process analysis and fine-tuning.

5.5. Integration with robot middleware and visualization tools

To facilitate the pallet loading optimizer's (PLO) integration and fine-tuning within robotized palletizing scenarios, software engineering activities focused on the integration of additional tools. The module is implemented within the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework [65], specifically ROS2 [66], to allow for seamless and effective communication between the automation modules and the execution resources. Interfaces have been created to expose the configuration variables and control the packaging process. ROS2 actions are used to initiate the packaging process and provide real-time feedback, allowing other modules to begin their calculations without waiting for the optimization to conclude. Additionally, this architecture can stop and restart the optimization from any state, offering additional flexibility. Both 2D and 3D visualizations of the pallet configuration are provided (Fig. 13), using images and ROS Robot Visualizer (RVIZ) respectively, which are updated in real-time.

5.6. Auxiliary functionalities for robotic system integration

5.6.1. Virtual input pallet generation and rendering

To streamline integration and testing, a tool has been developed for generating random input pallet configurations, simulating real-world packaging scenarios for the metal industry case study. This tool is integrated into ROS2 and allows users to request a random initial pallet configuration via a custom service, with configurable parameters. For more intuitive parameter customization, a web-based interface has been created, enabling users to select aluminum profile variants, specify their respective quantities, and adjust additional parameters.

The algorithm processes the provided details to create a random layout by positioning the aluminum profiles side by side, simulating an input pallet for the packaging station. For replicating additional stacking scenarios, the inclusion of "layering spacers" is also provided. The generated configurations are seamlessly integrated into ROS2 to spawn

the profiles into the scene using the module's 3D visualization tools, initiating a virtual automation scenario. The automated 3D photo-realistic rendering pipeline, illustrated in Fig. 14, has been developed for use with Blender or Nvidia Omniverse and utilizes the input pallet configuration to create a synthetic dataset. This dataset can be used for training machine learning models to identify and locate the objects in the initial stack, aiding in the development of a perception module for a fully automated robotized packaging scenario. Details for this perception system are outside the scope of this manuscript.

5.6.2. Loading dependencies calculation

An additional functionality of the pallet loading module is the ability to calculate dependencies between objects in the final packaging configuration. More specifically, the PLO is able to generate handling dependencies describing feasible handling sequences at given scenarios (e.g., loading of objects following a bottom-up order). In this direction, the module assigns each object a unique placement identifier and uses geometric data to determine the loading order. This is accomplished through an iterative algorithm that identifies overlaps in the projected volumes of the loaded objects.

As a result, a dependency array is generated for each object (Fig. 15). This array specifies the IDs of the objects that must be loaded before it. Since dependencies can be represented as a tree structure, a Depth First Search (DFS) algorithm is used to resolve each object's full dependency list. This dependency information is used for integrating a scheduling engine into the automation process (Fig. 2) as described in Section 3.

6. Results & discussion

To evaluate the performance of the proposed solution to the Pallet Loading Problem in this manuscript, a series of simulation experiments were conducted, extracting key evaluation metrics to assess palletization effectiveness.

For the experimental setup (Fig. 16), random collections of objects were generated, including objects from 30 different profile families with varying dimensions, derived from the architectural aluminum industry case study. For each simulation run, the virtual input pallet generation module, presented in Section 5.6.1, generated random quantities from the available profile families to create collections of the desired number of objects.

The recorded evaluation metrics for each palletization result are as follows:

1. **Profiles Placed %:** The percentage of total profiles successfully placed on the pallet.
2. **Packaging Density %:** Indicates how tightly the objects are packaged compared to their occupied volume.

Fig. 13. 2D and 3D representation of a pallet loading optimization scenario of 100 objects in the aluminum metal industry.

Fig. 14. Photorealistic rendering pipeline for synthetic data collection.

Fig. 15. Loading dependencies example for an optimized stacked pallet.

Fig. 16. Experimental setup and usage of the PLO module.

3. **Pallet Utilization %:** The percentage of the pallet’s volume capacity that is utilized.
4. **Cargo Volume Packaged %:** The volume of objects successfully packaged relative to the total cargo volume.

To evaluate and compare different selection methods for sequential object placement, each method was tested across 50 runs using

randomized object collections, while the placement optimization algorithm remained unchanged throughout all experiments. A run was considered complete either when all objects in the randomized collection were successfully placed on the pallet, or when a selected object could no longer be placed stably on the pallet due to space or stability constraints. The methods tested included four heuristic-based approaches using different metrics to generate the loading sequence, one

dynamic object selection method using a PPO-based DRL agent with integrated action masking, and a random object selection method to serve as a baseline.

The heuristic approaches involved different combinations of methods and metrics. The most representative methods included in the experiments are the following: a) Sorting objects in decreasing order of volume. b) Sorting objects in decreasing order of palletization fitness scores. c) Clustering objects based on their palletization fitness scores. d) Clustering objects based on their palletization fitness scores and further sorting them within each cluster by volume. The results of these experiments are presented in Fig. 17.

Analyzing the results, several key insights can be drawn. Contrary to intuition, selecting the next object randomly outperformed certain heuristic-based approaches. Surprisingly, the intuitive method of loading the largest objects first proved to be the worst-performing method across all recorded metrics. This poor performance is attributed to the creation of large gaps at the start of the sequential loading process, as the oversized objects fail to fit in these spaces, leading to pallet instability.

Similarly, sorting objects based solely on palletization fitness scores did not perform well. While this approach achieved high packaging density, it did so by prioritizing the placement of only the most "fitted" objects, at the cost of leaving many other objects unplaced. This is reflected in the low percentage of successfully placed objects. On the other hand, approaches that utilized clustering yielded more promising results and managed to outperform random object selection in most cases. Among the heuristic-based methods tested, the combination of clustering based on palletization fitness scores and sorting within clusters by object volume emerged as the top performer.

However, the most notable results were achieved using the dynamic object selection method powered by a Deep Reinforcement Learning agent. The DRL agent consistently outperformed all heuristic-based methods. It successfully placed over 99 % of the objects, on average, in each pallet loading scenario, while achieving a packaging density of

79.22 %, comparable to the palletization fitness sorting approach, which only managed to place around 88 % of the objects in each run.

What sets the DRL agent apart, though, is its consistency in successfully placing all requested objects onto the pallet. The Palletization Completion Rate—defined as the percentage of test runs in which all objects were successfully placed on the pallet—demonstrates this. As shown in Fig. 18, the DRL agent achieved a completion rate of 86 %, meaning that in 43 out of 50 test runs, all objects were placed successfully. In contrast, the closest competitor, the sorted clusters approach, only managed a completion rate of 36 %, leaving objects unplaced in 32 out of 50 runs.

These findings showcase the DRL agent's superiority in handling the complexities of the pallet loading problem when object selection is concerned. Its ability to consistently achieve near-perfect object selections has been an exceptional addition to the manuscript's proposed methodology.

Regarding time requirements, the experimental results demonstrate that there is no significant difference in runtime between the various selection methods in the proposed implementation. The DRL-based

Fig. 18. Palletization completion rate of different object selection methods.

Fig. 17. Performance of different object selection methods across key metrics.

selection method introduced a minimal overhead of approximately 2 ms, which accounts for the calculations needed for action masking, object selection, and the generation of the environment observation for the agent’s policy network. Using CPU parallelization for the constraint application and the calculation of the optimal placement configuration during each object placement, the proposed methodology achieved a placement frequency of 5 objects per second. This performance was achieved with a resolution of 1 mm on a standard European pallet along its length (1200 mm).

The time requirements were measured using a desktop PC with the following specifications: Intel® Core™ i7–9700 CPU @ 3.00 GHz × 8, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 SUPER, and 32 GB DDR4 RAM. The results indicated that the process cycle time was highly dependent on CPU capabilities, with an increased number of CPU threads significantly improving the time required for the palletization process.

To evaluate the time complexity of the proposed approach, an analysis of the necessary steps for a single object placement was conducted, along with their respective time complexities. The key parameters are defined as:

- n : The number of objects to be palletized.
- m : The number of candidate positions for object placement.
- m' : The number of candidate positions that satisfy the placement constraints.

For object selection using the DRL agent, the observation generation has a time complexity of $O(m)$, while action masking and selection are constant at $O(1)$. The application of constraints depends on the number of candidate positions, resulting in $O(m)$, whereas the optimization criteria are applied to the filtered set of positions, yielding $O(m')$. Since the placement process repeats for all n objects and $m' \leq m$, the overall asymptotic complexity aggregates to $O(n \times m)$. Thus, the time complexity of the proposed approach scales linearly with the number of objects and candidate positions.

In addition to the runtime computational costs of the proposed approach, there are overheads associated with preprocessing the objects and training the DRL model. However, the object preprocessing time is negligible. For the object families used in the experimental setup, the preprocessing step does not exceed 2 seconds and only needs to be executed once. On the other hand, training the DRL selector is considerably more time-intensive. Fig. 19 illustrates the average episode reward of the DRL agent during training, which spans approximately 1.9 million steps. As discussed in Section 5.2.2, a step in this context corresponds to an object selection, while each complete palletization process is considered an episode.

Using a desktop PC with the previously mentioned specifications, the training process required approximately 2 hours and 15 minutes, utilizing multithreading and GPU acceleration. The results indicate that the agent’s average reward increases rapidly during the first 800,000 steps,

as the agent continuously refines its selection policy. Between 800,000 and 1.3 million steps, the rate of improvement slows significantly, and from 1.3 to 1.9 million steps, further improvement is marginal. This plateau is likely because the outcome becomes increasingly dependent on the inherent potential of the random object collection rather than the agent’s decisions.

Action masking proved to be a critical component of this implementation. Without action masking, the training process failed to converge to a satisfactory level within a reasonable timeframe, as episodes ended prematurely due to the agent repeatedly selecting objects that were no longer available. Consequently, even after extensive training, the agent without action masking achieved less than 80 % of the average reward obtained by the agent trained with action masking. However, it is worth noting that action masking increases computational time during training by approximately 60 % for the same number of steps. Despite this additional time requirement, the significant performance improvement justifies its use.

In summary, the experimental results and observations during the development phase demonstrate that the combination of a DRL selector with placement optimization, using multi-criteria decision-making, consistently produced high-quality results for the manuscript’s case study. This approach successfully achieved the placement of over 100 irregularly shaped objects on a standard European pallet, closely resembling the arrangement depicted in Fig. 13. To highlight the framework’s capabilities, the tests utilized some of the most irregular object variants, with stability criteria selected to favor successful placement. However, for real-world applications, stricter constraints would be required. This aligns with current practices in the case study’s factory, where profiles are iteratively bundled after a few placements to account for potential instabilities.

Finally, the proposed solution has been designed for objects with uniform dimensions along one axis, and the search is restricted to two dimensions. However, an extension to a three-dimensional search is possible, by applying the same principles of the proposed framework.

7. Conclusions & future work

The work presented in this manuscript represents a significant advancement in the automation of packaging lines for objects with complex geometries, such as those wrapped in protective foil. By integrating Deep Reinforcement Learning, optimization algorithms, and heuristics, the proposed framework addresses the challenges inherent in handling irregularly shaped objects while ensuring practical applicability in industrial environments. Furthermore, the framework is highly configurable and adaptable to specific use cases, allowing end-users to calibrate thresholds and configure optimization criteria to meet their unique requirements.

Despite its strengths, the current solution exhibits certain limitations that suggest areas for further improvement. In the current

Fig. 19. Average episode reward for the maskable DRL selector over 1.9 million steps, visualized using TensorBoard.

implementation, the constraint filtering process does not consider dynamic factors like vibrations during transportation. This limitation could be addressed by introducing a minimum interlocking surface for each object placement—though this may reduce placement flexibility—or by incorporating a physics-based simulation, which would increase computational demands. Additionally, potential object deformations, such as wrapping compression or material elasticity, are not modeled. In scenarios involving highly complex objects and multiple placements, slight deviations in placement positions can propagate, potentially compromising the stability of the entire configuration. To address these issues, the framework is designed for integration with external monitoring modules, such as cameras, to enable real-time recalibration. This design establishes a feedback loop that enhances system resilience by enabling adaptation and recovery from disruptions while improving robustness by preventing disturbance propagation [67].

The optimization process also presents certain challenges. The evaluation of object orientations is restricted to predefined subsets, and the optimization criteria require careful design and calibration. Moreover, the DRL agent is closely tied to the specific placement optimization setup used during training. Migrating the solution to a different optimizer or significantly altering the optimization weights would necessitate re-training the DRL agent to achieve optimal results. With that in mind, a reasonable approach for new scenarios would involve initially employing a heuristic-based selection method until the optimization algorithm is well-defined, after which a DRL selector could be trained to maximize performance.

Future activities will focus on the deployment of the proposed framework in physical installation industrial scenarios. This will enable the calibration of constraints and optimization weights to reflect physical properties and improve stability. Advanced stability analysis will be pursued by incorporating a physics engine into the optimization loop or adopting sequential stability propagation techniques to mitigate cumulative instability. Additionally, the authors aim to extend the manuscript's proposed framework into three dimensions, explore the implementation of a Deep Reinforcement Learning agent for object placement, and investigate any margins for improvement in comparison to constraint satisfaction programming. Finally, to ensure greater module acceptance and usability, even for users having less programming experience, the design of intuitive graphical user interfaces is foreseen.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Theodoropoulos Nikolaos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Andronas Dionisis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Kampourakis Emmanouil:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Makris Sotiris:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

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